

USING INORGANIC SAMPLE TO MAKE HANGING PLANT POT CRAFT IN GAMPONG BAGOK PANAH DUA

T. Edyansyah¹, Muhammad Roni², Amru Usman³, Em Yusuf Iis⁴,
Rusydi Abubakar⁵, Rico Nur Ilham⁶
^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Universitas Malikussaleh, Indonesia.

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Abstract

This community service activity aims to address the problem of poorly managed inorganic waste in Bagok Panah Dua Village, Darul Aman District, East Aceh Regency. The local community, predominantly farmers, faces an increasing amount of waste that can negatively impact their health and the environment. One solution offered is to process inorganic waste, especially used bottles, into handicrafts in the form of hanging plant pots. Through training and mentoring, the community is provided with skills to recycle waste into products with economic value, while simultaneously raising awareness of the importance of waste management. This activity was carried out using an empowerment-based approach, where the community is invited to actively participate in sorting and recycling waste at the household level. The results of this activity demonstrated high enthusiasm from the community who successfully utilized used bottles to create marketable plant pots. In addition, this activity also succeeded in raising environmental awareness and having a positive impact on the community's economy. Despite several obstacles, such as a lack of additional resources to beautify the products, this activity still managed to provide significant benefits to the community of Bagok Panah Dua Village.

Keywords: *Community service, inorganic waste, recycling, handicrafts, hanging plant pots.*

INTRODUCTION

The community of Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, located in Darul Aman District, East Aceh Regency, faces serious problems related to waste management, particularly inorganic waste. As the population continues to grow, so does consumer behavior, impacting the amount of waste generated daily. Inorganic waste, such as plastic, used bottles, and other packaging, is often not managed properly, and much is simply discarded without considering its negative impact on the environment. This ineffective waste management can lead to various serious environmental problems. Accumulated waste can cause flooding, the spread of disease, produce unpleasant odors, and even damage the natural beauty and air quality. Poorly managed waste can also pollute the soil and water, ultimately impacting public health. On the other hand, the community of Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, which relies largely on the agricultural sector, has not yet utilized the potential of existing waste as a resource that can be processed and generated profit.

The process of collecting waste in the village environment

waste sorting process

Inorganic waste, often considered useless, can be recycled into economically valuable products if managed properly. One solution offered in this community service activity is the utilization of inorganic waste, particularly used bottles, to create hanging plant pots. In addition to reducing the amount of waste polluting the environment, these hanging plant pot crafts can also provide economic benefits to the community. The increasingly popular trend of growing ornamental plants among the public, especially housewives, opens up a significant market opportunity for this product.

Formulation of the problem

Based on the problems faced by the Gampong Bagok Panah Dua community, there are several main issues that need to be addressed in this community service activity, including:

1. Lack of Public Knowledge About Waste Utilization
The community in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua still has limited knowledge about how to process inorganic waste into useful products. Most waste, especially plastic, is considered non-reusable and is simply thrown away. A lack of education about the importance of recycling waste into useful products is a major obstacle.
2. Lack of Public Awareness of the Environment Polluted by Waste
Most people lack awareness of the negative impacts of waste on health and the environment. Furthermore, low levels of active participation in waste management activities make this problem even more difficult to resolve. There is no collective effort by the community to reduce waste in their surroundings.

Activity Objectives

The objectives of this community service activity are as follows:

1. Increasing Community Income Through Handicrafts
This activity aims to provide training to the community in processing inorganic waste, particularly used bottles, into handicrafts such as hanging plant pots. These products not only beautify the environment but can also be sold to increase community income.
2. Increasing Public Awareness About Good Waste Management
In addition to providing skills, this activity also aims to raise public awareness about the importance of proper waste management. Residents are encouraged to sort their waste at home, recycle inorganic waste, and utilize it for more productive and environmentally friendly purposes.
3. Encouraging a Healthy Mindset and Concern for Environmental Cleanliness
Through this activity, it is hoped that the community will not only gain new skills but also change their mindset about the importance of maintaining environmental cleanliness and sustainability. This will

encourage them to be more active in maintaining environmental cleanliness and reducing the negative impacts of waste.

Benefits of Activities

The benefits of this community service activity are extensive and are expected to have positive impacts in both the short and long term. Some of the anticipated benefits include:

1. **Cultivating Community Creativity**
This activity will encourage people to think creatively about utilizing inorganic waste. With the skills they gain, they can create a variety of useful products, including hanging plant pots, pencil cases, and other decorative items, which they can sell to generate income.
2. **Providing Alternative Income to the Community**
Through this training, residents of Gampong Bagok Panah Dua will acquire skills that can improve their economy. Craft products made from inorganic waste can be sold to local consumers and the wider market, opening up new opportunities for increased income.
3. **Reducing the Negative Impact of Waste on the Environment**
By managing inorganic waste through recycling, the amount of waste being disposed of carelessly can be reduced. This will mitigate negative environmental impacts, such as soil and water pollution, and reduce the risk of disease spread due to accumulated waste.
4. **Improving the Quality of Life and Public Health**
Proper waste management will create a cleaner and healthier environment, which in turn will improve the community's quality of life. A clean environment can reduce the potential for disease transmission and increase comfort. With these various benefits, this activity is expected to be the first step for the residents of Gampong Bagok Panah Dua to manage waste in a more productive and sustainable manner. Furthermore, this activity also aims to educate the community on how to maintain environmental cleanliness independently, without relying on outside parties, and encourage them to utilize waste as a valuable resource.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Waste management is a process involving the systematic and continuous reduction, sorting, collection, transportation, and disposal of waste. According to Law No. 18 of 2008, waste management must be carried out with the principles of responsibility and sustainability, and utilize waste as a reusable resource. Effective waste management not only reduces negative impacts on the environment but can also improve people's quality of life. The benefits of good waste management include facilitating the process of recycling inorganic waste into useful products, improving community welfare through the economic potential of recycling, and creating a healthier and cleaner environment. A proper recycling process can also reduce the amount of waste accumulated and minimize the impact of environmental pollution.

METHOD

Problem Solving Framework

To address the waste problem in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, a community empowerment approach was implemented through skills training in recycling inorganic waste, particularly used bottles, into hanging plant pots. This approach aims to raise community awareness of the importance of waste management and provide practical skills that can increase their income. Furthermore, the program aims to improve environmental conditions by reducing the amount of unmanaged waste.

Problem Solving Realization

The activity began with an outreach session on the importance of proper waste management and the benefits of recycling. This was followed by practical training on how to utilize used bottles as hanging plant pots. The community was provided with materials on how to sort waste, process it, and create marketable products. Participants were also given guidance on how to market their handicrafts to increase income.

Target Audience

This activity is aimed at the entire community in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, with a focus on housewives and groups interested in utilizing inorganic waste. The program is expected to reach a wider community and positively impact their skills and well-being.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stages of making flower pots (waste processing)

Implementation and Administration of Community Service

The community service program in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua proceeded smoothly and successfully. The activity began with an outreach session on the importance of waste management and how to sort inorganic waste for recycling. The community enthusiastically participated in the training session, which was conducted in an interactive and hands-on manner. After gaining a basic understanding, they immediately practiced making hanging plant pots from used bottles, which were then decorated to enhance their aesthetic value. Community involvement in every stage of the activity demonstrates a growing awareness of the importance of waste management and recycling. The entire community, especially housewives, actively participated, collecting used bottles and practicing plant pot-making techniques under the guidance of the community service team.

Evaluation and Results

Evaluation of this activity demonstrated that the community had benefited significantly from the training. Most participants successfully created hanging plant pots in various models and designs. Some products have even been exhibited and sold at local markets, receiving positive feedback from buyers. This demonstrates that this activity has not only successfully raised environmental awareness but also created new economic opportunities for the community. Furthermore, people are now more environmentally conscious, with many starting to sort and recycle their waste at home. This initiative has also fostered a spirit of mutual cooperation among communities that previously paid little attention to waste management.

Supporting Factors

Some factors that support the success of this activity include:

- **Community Participation** : High enthusiasm from the community in participating in training and practice made this activity run smoothly.
- **Support from Village Officials** : Support from village officials, especially the Geusyik of Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, is very important in facilitating the smooth running of activities.
- **Skills and Creativity** : The community has high creativity, especially in processing waste into handicrafts that have sales value.

Inhibiting Factors

Although this activity was successful, there were several challenges faced:

- **Lack of Initial Knowledge** : Some people do not fully understand the importance of waste sorting and management, so they need more time to understand and implement the methods taught.

- Limited Resources : Some participants had difficulty in providing additional materials to beautify plant pots, such as paint and other decorations, which can increase the selling value of the product.

Overall, despite some obstacles, the implementation of this activity showed positive results and had a significant impact on increasing public awareness of the importance of waste management and the economic potential that can be obtained from waste recycling.

CONCLUSION

Based on the implementation of community service activities in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua, it can be concluded that this activity successfully achieved its intended objectives. The community demonstrated high enthusiasm in participating in the training on recycling inorganic waste, particularly used bottles, into hanging plant pots. This activity not only raised public awareness about the importance of proper waste management but also provided new economic opportunities by utilizing waste into valuable products. Furthermore, the community is now more concerned about environmental cleanliness and has begun practicing waste management at the household level. Despite several obstacles, such as a lack of initial knowledge about waste management and limited resources, this activity still ran well and had a positive impact on improving the skills, creativity, and welfare of the community.

Suggestion

Some suggestions that can be given for the sustainability of this activity are:

1. Improve waste management education and training programs for the community so that their knowledge continues to grow.
2. Providing further support in the form of additional materials, such as paint and decorations, to beautify craft products so that they have higher market appeal.
3. Promote independent waste management efforts at the household level to maintain environmental cleanliness and health in Gampong Bagok Panah Dua.
4. With these steps, it is hoped that waste management and utilization can continue to develop and provide long-term benefits to the community.

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